

POWER LAWS IN ATOMIC AND MOLECULAR SPECTRA

Andrés Sáiz Martínez

Departamento de Astronomía y Astrofísica.

Facultad de Ciencias Matemáticas.

Universidad de Valencia.

Doctor Moliner, 50. 46100 Burjasot. Valencia. Spain.

Abstract: In this paper the spectral lines of the spectra of complex systems as the atoms and molecules are studied. The processes and energies involved in the production of the spectra are different. However, they show similar statistical characteristics in line intensities, as power laws and exponential tails. We are in a Self Organized Criticality (SOC) scenario, the fractal structures found in the spectra of some atoms and molecules in previous papers fit in such a scenario. This analysis allows us to make a new approach to the quantic phenomenon of the energy emission from the point of view of complexity. This new insight address interesting questions about the organization of the system and about the involved processes in the emission of energy.

Keywords: Complex Systems Spectra Statistical Properties SOC

Resumen: En este artículo se estudian las líneas espectrales de sistemas complejos como los átomos y moléculas. Los procesos y las energías implicadas en la producción de los espectros son diferentes. Sin embargo, muestran similares características en la distribución de intensidades de las líneas, como leyes de potencia y colas exponenciales. Se propone un escenario de Self Organized Criticality (SOC) en el que el comportamiento fractal encontrado en espectros de algunos átomos y moléculas en papers previos, encaja en este escenario. Este análisis nos permite aproximarnos al fenómeno cuántico de la emisión de la energía desde el punto de vista de la complejidad. Esta nueva perspectiva propone cuestiones interesantes sobre la organización del sistema y sobre los procesos implicados en la emisión de la energía.

Palabras clave: Sistemas Complejos Espectros Propiedades Estadísticas SOC

1 - Introduction

Bak, Tang and Wiesenfeld (BTW) {Bak87} suggest in their paper that the systems constituted by many elements in interaction can show some kind of characteristic behavior. The kind of systems suggested by BTW are dynamic systems that autoorganize themselves in a critical state with similar characteristics such as the thermodynamics systems in the phase transition temperature, although without the intervention of any special tuning. Since the publication of the broadly cited paper of BTW have been discovered a large quantity of dynamic systems of this kind, such as earthquakes, piles of sand, fires in the forests, random Boolean networks, etc.. The ubiquity of this kind of systems seems to confirm the suggestion of BTW. The main characteristic that allows us to recognize this kind of systems is the response to external perturbations. This response is characterized by statistical distributions following power laws and, usually, with fractal structure and with exponential tails above a certain scale. It is known that the spectra of atoms and molecules complex enough, shows fractal structure {Saiz96,Klafter92,Saiz99}. In the case of the atoms the fractal structure was analyzed in the space of wavelengths and in the molecular case, in

the space of frequencies. In this paper we will analyze other elements of the Self Organized Criticality (SOC) as the power laws and exponential tails. We will study the rotational spectrum of some organic and inorganic molecules at 300 K and the spectra of some atoms. As we will show, the power laws obtained in molecules and in atoms are good clues to consider these systems as good candidates to exhibit SOC.

2 - Spectra

The rotational lines of the molecular spectra, have been obtained from the JPL Molecular Spectroscopy Team {Pickett98}. The molecules analyzed are the following: Acrylonitrile (C₂H₃CN), 75697 lines, Dimethyl Ether (CH₃OCH₃), 21735 lines, Hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂), 38357 lines, Peroxynitric acid (HOONO₂), 50775 lines, Butyronitrile (C₃H₇CN), 131349 lines, Nitrogen dioxide (NO₂), 16444 lines, Ethyl formate (C₂H₅OOCH), 60671 lines, Nitric acid (HNO₃), 36551 lines and Ethyl Cyanide (C₂H₅CN), 52883 lines. Among others data, for each line we have the frequency in MHz and the integrated intensity in nm² Mhz at 300 K. The rank of frequencies of the lines of each molecule is

different in each case, but all of them between 10^{-1} and 10^4 Ghz. The data of the atomic spectra have been obtained from the NIST

{Sansonetti92}. In this case, the analysed spectra are: Pt I, 859 lines, Pt II, 2060 lines, Ne I, 1224 lines and Ne II, 818 lines, in the wavelength laying between 1130 and 4330 Angstroms. These spectra have been selected according to the line intensities processing; Sansonetti et al found only small variations in the relative intensities of lines in their lamps. Nevertheless, it is not certain that other lamps would exhibit identical properties. In general, other data related to this kind of spectra have few lines or, if many, neglect the information related with the intensities.

3. Power Laws

Data of the previous section come from systems different in many ways; in molecules we have differences among the number of atoms that compose each molecule and the spectra have a rotational origin, while in the atomic case the spectrum comes from electric transitions produced by the interaction with a electromagnetic field. However, in molecules and in atoms we found fractal behavior {Saiz96,Klafter92}; in the atomic case the wavelengths distribution of the spectral lines was analyzed, and, in the molecular case, the intensities of the spectral lines were analyzed. We cant assure the same kind of behavior for all kinds of molecules or atoms, because it seems to exist a relation with the complexity of the system. The complexity, consequence of the large number of degrees of freedom involved, and the fractal behavior, are some of the characteristics of systems that show SOC; may be the atoms and molecules analyzed will show the same behavior. Because of that, we will look for the existence of power laws.

The histogram of energies in the studied spectra does not result in power laws. However, the histogram of the line intensities apparition frequency in a spectrum, $N(I)$ is a function of the intensity I , and follows a power law $N(I)=aI^b$, figure(1) and figure(2).

The fits carried out allows us to estimate the exponents b . The results obtained for b are the following:

$$b_{C_2H_3CN}=-1.15\pm 0.02; \quad b_{CH_3OCH_3}=-0.65\pm 0.01; \quad b_{H_2O_2}=-0.800\pm 0.007; \quad b_{HOONO_2}=-1.19\pm 0.01; \quad b_{C_3H_7CN}=-0.818\pm 0.008; \quad b_{NO_2}=-0.96\pm 0.01; \quad b_{C_2H_5OCH}=-0.87\pm 0.03; \quad b_{HNO_3}=-0.842\pm 0.008; \quad b_{C_2H_5CN}=-0.98\pm 0.01$$

$$b_{Pt-II}=-1.62\pm 0.03; \quad b_{Pt-I}=-2.01\pm 0.05 \\ b_{Ne-II}=-2.3\pm 0.1; \quad b_{Ne-I}=-3.0\pm 0.2$$

Fig. 1. Log-log histogram for the intensity I , with $N(I)$ frequency of apparition of the intensities. In this picture we show four of the nine analyzed spectra. The experimental data of the spectra of C_2H_3CN (triangles), H_2O_2 (squares), C_3H_7CN (solid circles) and C_2H_5CN (circles), fit power laws as $N(I)=aI^b$ in ranks usually bigger than a decade. The power laws derived from the fits are the straight lines at which the experimental data are fitted.

Although it seems that, looking at the slopes, the atoms with spectra Pt I and Pt II behave like different systems, we should keep in mind that the lack of statistics can affect the estimation of the exponents. In the molecular case we observe that, at high values of intensity, the fitted power law has, in almost all the cases, exponential tails like $N(I)=c.exp(-dI)$, as shown in figure(3). In the atomic case cannot be adjusted an exponential tail by a severe lack of statistics.

Fig.2 Log-log histogram of intensities for the spectrum Pt II (square) and for Pt I (circles). The straight lines represented show how the data fit powerlaws $N(I)=aI^b$, Pt I spectrum (dotted) and Pt II spectrum (dashed). For the analyzed atoms the rank of fitting is approximately one decade.

4. Avalanches

The results we have are similar to the ones that appear in multitude of systems that show SOC; sand piles {Bak87}, random Boolean networks {Luque01}, earthquakes {Scholz90, Scholz91, Sornette91, Chen91}, etc... Therefore, our systems (atoms and molecules), which are complex in the sense of many coupled elements, are candidates to show SOC, as the above cited systems. The interpretation in terms of SOC allows us to identify the intensity I , as the avalanche in the system. However, the intensity is the result of the contribution of each excited atom or molecule, and the result of a measurement and production process. The excitation conditions are produced at very low pressures. Therefore, if we assume that a particle doesn't affect other particles in the process of the emission of energy, the properties of the intensity should be transferred to the probability of transition among different states in interaction with an electromagnetic field. Nevertheless, materials (magnesium fluoride windows of the lamps), devices or implemented techniques can change intensities. In any case, we detect powerlaws in intensities produced by the system atoms/molecules-spectrum production system-measurement system; and if we suppose that intensities are not significantly altered in the process of production and measurement of the spectrum, atoms or molecules individually behave like a system that exhibit SOC. In this case, avalanches are the probabilities of transition among different states of each atom or molecule.

We have verified that, in almost all the cases, it exists a crossover to an exponential tail above a specific value of intensity. In other systems that exhibit SOC this behavior is associated to physical or geometrical factors that limits the size of the avalanches; size of the sand pile, thickness of the crust in the earthquakes and number of automaton in random Boolean networks. In the analysis of the atoms there are variations in the low wavelength transmission of the magnesium fluoride windows of different lamps {Sansonetti92} that affect to the relative intensities among different zones of the spectrum. Besides, elements as the transparency or thickness of the windows should affect mainly small intensities. However, in molecules attenuation affects at large intensities. This attenuation would be due to the lack of dynamic range of the different involved devices, but we can't deduce this from the references previously cited. Therefore, this attenuation seems somehow intrinsic to the process of emission although, in our case, we have not found geometrical or physical factors related to molecules or atoms that limit the process. If all the studied systems showed the same powerlaw with variations related to the crossover,

we would think that all of them are reduced to the same category of behavior but with different physical or geometrical magnitudes which limit the avalanches. However, we have different power laws; although the data, see figure(3), suggest that can exist families of systems which could show this behavior. The studied systems don't show, apparently, a specific tuning; the power laws appear in molecules slightly excited and in one time ionized atoms. Besides, data come from different teams and devices in the case of molecules, and from different lamps in the case of atoms; the power law response seems to be

produced in a broad rank of conditions.

Fig.3 Log log histogram, in the same conditions that the previous figures. The spectra are: H₂O₂ (square) and C₃H₇CN (circles). They have a very similar exponent in the powerlaw. As it can be observed, exponential tails fit correctly the experimental data; results are: $d_{H_2O_2}=57\pm 2$ (dashed) and $d_{C_3H_7CN}=8000\pm 200$ (dot dashed)

5. – Conclusions

The complexity of atoms and molecules comes from the contribution of a large number of degrees of freedom. This complexity justifies the consideration of a scenario SOC in which the fractality of spectra is an expected element. In spite of the complexity of this kind of systems there are statistical properties described by simple power laws, as occurs in systems that exhibit SOC. If we suppose that the atoms and molecules analyzed belong to this category of systems, we will assume that the system, extremely space and time correlated, reacts to the perturbations as a whole. In atoms and molecules the relaxation is conducted by an internal process that carries the system of an energetic level to another one. However, this process does not connect always the two same levels but, given a specific initial level, the frequency at which final levels are connected is

different. We can characterize the avalanche generated by the internal process by the emitted energy in the case of the earthquakes or by the number of automaton involved in changes, in random Boolean network. In our case, the avalanche is the probability of transition in the change from a superior level to another inferior level. The consideration of this kind of avalanches presents two problems that remain open; the first one is to propose models that reproduce this probabilistic behavior; and the second one, the physical interpretation of the avalanche in terms of probability, although probably the solution of one problem depends on the other one.

We have a large number of spectral lines available for the analyzed molecules. In contrast, the number of lines in the case of the atoms is scarce. A large number of correctly processed data in the intensity, would conduct to interesting conclusions about the level of complexity at which power laws appear. The results obtained allows us to approach the class of quantic phenomena analyzed from the complexity point of view, and gives the possibility to create non quantic models of the system. In the new approach to the emission of energy in a SOC scenario, the probability of transition between levels is considered as a process composed by multiple steps.

9. Gratiudes

Gratiudes to Fernando Ballesteros by the critical reading of the text. This work is supported by the 'Ministerio de Ciencia y Tecnología. Acciones Especiales. Marco del Plan Nacional de Investigación Científica, Desarrollo e Innovación Tecnológica', entitled: 'La Teoría del Caos y su aplicación a la detección y control de eventuales dinámicas caóticas en sistemas complejos biológicos y sociales'. Principal investigator: Lorenzo Ferrer Figueras. Grant N° BFM2001-5515-E, tipo A2

10. References

- {Bak87} P. Bak and C. Tang and K. Wiesenfeld, 1987, Phys. Rev. Lett., **59**, 381
- {Saiz96}, A. Sáiz and V.J. Martínez, 1996, Phys. Rev. E, **54**, 2431
- {Klafter92}, E. Shalev and J. Klafter and D.F. Plusquellic and D.W. Pratt, 1992, Physica A", **191**, 186
- {Saiz99}, A. Sáiz and V.J. Martínez", 1999, Phys. Rev. E., **60**, 4993
- {Pickett98}, H.M. Pickett and R.L. Poynter and E.A. Cohen and M.L. Delitsky and J.C. Pearson and H.S.P. Muller, 1998, J. Quant. Spectrosc. and

Rad. Transfer, **60**, 883

{Sansonetti92}, J.E. Sansonetti and J. Reader and C.J. Sansonetti and N. Acquista, 1992, J. of Research of the NIST, **97**, 1

{Luque01}, B. Luque and F.J. Ballesteros and M. Muro, 2001, Phys. Rev. E, **63**, 51913

{Scholz90}, C.H. Scholz, "The Mechanics of Earthquakes and Faulting", Cambridge University Press, 1990

{Scholz91}, C.H. Scholz., 1991, T. Riste and D. Sherrington, Kluwer,

{Sornette91}, D. Sornette, 1991, in T. Riste and D. Sherrington (eds.), Kluwer

{Chen91}, K. Chen and P. Bak and S.P. Obukhov, 1991, Phys. Rev. A, **43**, 625